

Academic indigenous lands:¹

Connecting academics with the indigenous community, a Bolivian case study

Abstract

Language data of endangered indigenous languages are being recorded, analysed, and uploaded to archives that are supposed to be accessible for everyone, including the speech community. However, there are certain obstacles. Access to the archives, data, and publications often turns out to be a great challenge that is difficult to overcome under the actual conditions. In parts, the ambitious ethical aims may be hypocritical, a conflict for researchers, who often publish exclusively for the scientific community. The people that are studied turn into research objects and hardly play active roles in the documentation and description of their own languages. The examples presented here include the researcher's own solutions to this problem and demonstrates a case study with the Guarayu people.

Keywords: ethics, language documentation, endangered languages, language archives, accessibility

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When languages are documented, the funders or researchers have certain demands they should meet with respect to the community whose language is being documented: ethical claims require them to give back something to the community, at least, if not letting the speakers participate actively in the investigation and publications of the outcomes. This article does not only reflect upon the difficulties that researchers as the author herself might face in trying to fulfil the mentioned criteria of ethically correct fieldwork, but it also shows her personal solutions and ways of meeting at least parts of her own aims of integrating indigenous peoples in the academic world and the outcomes and aims of linguistic investigation.

¹ This article was written after the presentation of the subject under the same title at the international conference: "Multi-platform and Connecting Communities: Contemporary Challenges for Minority Language Media", 31 March – 1 April 2022, Europa-Universität Flensburg (Germany), organized by Sergiusz Bober, Miren Manias-Muñoz, & Craig Willis. I am very grateful for the useful comments on the presentation and the article by the organizers.

1. Introduction

Since the year 2003, I have been documenting a number of indigenous languages of Bolivia, South America. These undertakings were funded by the DobeS and the ELDP programmes (§3), among others. The language data have been recorded, analysed, and uploaded to digital archives, which conserves data of highly endangered languages – at least for the world-wide academic community. Despite ethical declarations (cf. §4), the language community does usually not have access to these data for various reasons (cf. §5). The ambitious ethical aims of conserving language data may be conceived as somewhat hypocritical, if it is only a data corpus preserved for the research community. Researchers like me then publish articles on issues of scientific interest, easily apt to turning the speech community into bare “objects of investigation”, rather than letting them be the subjects they really are (cf. Agunloye, 2019, pp. 171ff.). In this article, I analyse these difficulties and show my personal solutions for the indigenous communities I have worked with.

In §2, there is an introduction into the area of study: the Bolivian plurilingual setting. Which Bolivian languages are found in which digital archives is sketched in §3. The ethical demands on researchers when collecting language data in the light of decolonization (a concept propagated in Bolivia since 2009), is the focus in §4 and a reflection on the difficulties to meet these demands in §5, where my own investigation in Bolivia is summarized. §6 goes into detail of the case study of this article, and I present the (digital) activities I have been entertaining with the Guarayo people, among which I was living for 5 years. These activities include a Facebook page with high publicity in the indigenous digital community, keyboard installations for computers and smartphones, and the physical reproduction of my academic publications on the Guarayo language in a local journal. §7 holds some final remarks on the points discussed in the article: How much are indigenous communities involved in linguistic investigation, and how can they get access to the academic world and become part of it? Which issues have been resolved, and which remain open debates and problems?

2. The plurilingual country of Bolivia

The geographical focus lies here on Bolivia² in South America, which is where the case study brings us. This country looks back on a half a millennium long colonial history with Spanish that conquered the linguistic diversity. In this setting the indigenous languages are increasingly endangered and their usage declines.

The Plurinational State of Bolivia lists 36 official indigenous languages in its New Constitution (CPE, 2009), and there are current attempts to include three more languages in a new version of this list (cf. Danielsen & Terhart, 2024). In view of the strong tendency towards Latin American Spanish homogenization (cf. Danielsen, 2021), the official acceptance and visibility of indigenous languages have been propagated in the past 20 years to prevent the extinction and disappearance of many languages in the country. Even more languages have been registered at some point in the written history of today’s Bolivian territory (cf. Danielsen, 2016), i.e., 54 languages, belonging to at least 13 language families, in addition to six more linguistic isolates, one mixed language and one creole. Out of the presently recognized official languages, the majority are rather endangered and count less than 10,000 speakers – only five languages have more speakers, and only about 12 languages are still spoken on a daily basis. Bolivian peoples do not have any written records of the e.g. very powerful Inka Empire. There were multilingual language policies in the Inka Empire, however, these were not written down. In the lowlands of Bolivia, there was no written tradition either. The first people to take written notes on this linguistic diversity were the Jesuit priests (and people around them), who applied the languages in sermons and for their mission. While Catholic missionization in South America must be viewed critically, these Jesuit priests have been the first and last ones to document many a language, and finally, they helped preserving the dominant ones through the translated bible parts

² Correctly, the country has changed from the “Republic of Bolivia” to the “Plurinational State of Bolivia” in 2009.

and prayers. Smaller languages, of course, that were made into minority languages in mission towns, also suffered the discrimination and earlier loss under these circumstances.

However, the history of contact with indigenous peoples in Bolivia does not only show linguistic support measures. There are at least two other courses that were taken for rather despicable reasons. In the early 20th century, the Republic of Bolivia followed the politics of “pacification” of the forest tribes, and thus contacted many people and taught them Spanish, among other cultural assimilation strategies. Later, after 1952, when the MNR³ party came into power, the state had the goal of a Spanish homogenization, apparently with the will of integrating all people of the country in the educational system and official activities. Evangelic missionizer linguists of the SIL⁴ were invited to teach Spanish to speakers of indigenous languages in the country. This caused rapid language loss, and many Bolivian lowland languages have had their last (monolingual) mother tongue speakers in the 1950s.

In the turn of growing indigenous movements in Bolivia in the 1990s, the linguistic and cultural diversity under threat started to receive international attention (cf. Danielsen & Terhart, 2024). Consequently, linguists from different countries and with different financial support began recording and documenting especially small, endangered languages of Bolivia.

3. Language archives with digitalized Bolivian languages

The first larger digital data collections is gathered in the AILLA of the University of Texas (*The Archive of the Indigenous Languages of Latin America*, since 2000), with 17 Bolivian languages and data ranging from short word lists up to some transcribed texts with audio files. The other two larger endeavours brought many linguists to Bolivia: the DobeS programme (*Dokumentation bedrohter Sprachen*, 2003–2013) financed by the Volkswagen foundation and the still on-going ELDP (*Endangered Languages Documentation Programme*, since 2004), formerly at SOAS in London, recently moved to the Berlin Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities. These two programmes have created the largest linguistic archives with video and audio data, transcribed and analysed texts, dictionaries, and other materials. The DobeS archive physically sits at the Max Planck Institute of Psycholinguistics at Nijmegen, Holland, as part of *The Language Archive* (TLA). The number of languages exceeds 100 (cf. Volkswagenstiftung, 2013), including four Bolivian languages. The ELDP keeps data in the digital archive named ELAR (*Endangered Languages Archive*), where more than 740 languages have been documented, among them 12 Bolivian languages. In the past years, new activities can be observed and the language documentation has expanded immensely; archives are growing and coming up, such as the DoReCo (*Language Documentation Reference Corpus*), some local/ national initiatives, like the archive at the CAICYT/CONICET in Buenos Aires, the DILA (*Documentación e Investigación en Lingüística y Antropología*), and certainly many others world-wide.

4. New ethics, decolonization, and equity

During colonization, South America has suffered on many different levels, among them the discrimination, exclusion, and ignorance of indigenous peoples.⁵ In the course of 500 years, many indigenous groups were assimilated, disappeared, and linguistic & cultural diversity are under threat. Indigenous peoples and their languages were contacted by European colonizers and settlers, they were described and studied by European missionizers and travellers, and last but not least, the data and information are investigated by European scientists in any possible field of research.⁶ Nowadays,

³ Movimiento Nacionalista Revolucionario

⁴ Summer Institute of Linguistics

⁵ Not to speak of genocides, exploitation, violence, and diseases that Europeans brought.

⁶ One good example are the many projects with and around the Chimane/Tsimane people in Bolivia, of whom scientists have a special interest, be it in medical studies, or ecological, linguistic, sociological, etc. – I would call them “totally over researched”, and I believe that this is rather exploited by researchers applying for grants than put into question.

we can still observe the global results of colonization and inequity in science, where equity may be an aim, but the actual reality is a “race gap” in academia (cf. Graves et al., 2022, Chen et al., 2022). However, the standing is different in the 21st century than it was in the 15th.

Science and in particular field research have changed a lot in the past decades, and investigators as well as institutions are very careful to meet ethical guidelines and behave socially and ethically appropriately in the field and when working with people. This can be observed by the many published ethical guidelines at institutions, such as the Max Planck Institutes or their umbrella Max-Planck-Gesellschaft (MPG, 2021),⁷ and you can also expect ethics to be referred to in project applications (cf. Austin, 2010; §5). This “ethic fashion” is certainly a measure that is related to the colonial guilt that investigators and investigating institutions feel. “Is it not again a kind of ‘scientific colonization’ what they are doing?”, is a question we often hear in the field, at least from the more eloquent people. Ethical guidelines are there to protect the researcher from wrong conclusions and suspicions; they are there for the people in the field to secure their treatment as ethically correct; and they are something to build on in the future, something to guarantee the quality of the data, and especially for future re-uses of the data collection to be permitted.

This is the way how our world is functioning nowadays: “just say you are good and accord to everything that is expected from you to be politically, ethically, socially correct in your behaviour, and you are good”, one could argue polemically. Of course, the world is not that easy. It is hard enough to actually accord to these ethics in the field, to NOT hurt anybody’s feelings, to NOT exclude anybody from your investigation – well, I would actually say, it is impossible to be like that. But today’s world expects us to be just the opposite of all that our ancestors have committed and done wrong.

Decolonization in Bolivia is an attempt to build new structures that create behaviour opposite to that brought by the century-long colonizing structures. The general idea should be defined as follows:

La descolonización es, en sentido estricto, el proceso mediante el cual los pueblos que fueron despojados del autogobierno mediante la invasión extranjera, recuperan su autodeterminación. La descolonización es un proceso básico de liberación y de autonomía. La descolonización tiene como consecuencia ineluctable la independencia. (Pedro Portugal in Vicepresidencia, 2011, p. 19)⁸

This movement, established in the new government and the CPE since 2009, has been criticized a lot from the right-wing opposition in lowland Bolivia. This is also partly because of the interpretation with the Inca Empire as the point of departure and arrival, which is by far not the most common understanding of decolonization in Bolivia, but the fear of many lowland Bolivians:

‘La descolonización, entendemos nosotros, es continuar el camino de integración y unidad que bajo la forma de la “sociedad de los Inkas” los españoles encontraron y desestructuraron en la invasión iniciada en 1532’. (ibid., p. 20)⁹

Thus, National Bolivians not belonging to any indigenous group, but also lowland Bolivian indigenous peoples felt excluded from this decolonization model. Nevertheless, it has not been taken to such an extreme, and even though some presumable Andean ideals have been promoted, such as the *Buen Vivir* ‘good living’ (*Sumaq Kawsay* in Quechua and *Suma Qamaña* in Aymara), Aymara New Year and Quechua and Aymara festivities, the Bolivian Ministry of Education and one of its executing institutions, the IPELC¹⁰, rather support the plurinationality and plurilingualism of the country. This means that decolonization has indeed started as being the great hope of many a discriminated group

⁷ Ethical Guidelines of the Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, 2021, partly summarized at <https://www.eva.mpg.de/primat/ethical-guidelines/>

⁸ English translation: Decolonization is, strictly speaking, the process by which peoples who were deprived of self-government by foreign invasion, recover their self-determination. Decolonization is a basic process of liberation and autonomy. Decolonization has the inevitable consequence of independence.

⁹ English translation: ‘Decolonization, we understand, is to continue the path of integration and unity that the Spaniards found and deconstructed in the form of the “Inka society” in the invasion that began in 1532’.

¹⁰ Instituto Plurinacional de Lengua y Cultura

of people in Bolivia. And there are already notable outcomes. In the year 2023, almost every officially approved language has its representative institution (ILCs)¹¹, leading initiatives to teach the languages, and to revitalize all the very small ones.

Indigenous peoples profit from this concept in different ways, however, the world can neither be turned to spin towards the other direction, nor can we always be good.

5. Digital language documentation and the conflicts

The language archives introduced in §3 have been created with the claim that the many small languages in the world that are endangered to disappear, thus the world's cultural heritage, should be documented and stored for the (academic) world and also for the language group and the members of the ethnic groups and their descendants. The languages that would be classified as endangered are listed in the UNESCO *Atlas of the World's Languages in Danger* (2011). Now, the DobeS programme was e.g. created as an answer to this world-wide endangerment, and funding based on the aim to document the world's linguistic diversity. When the programme started and applications ran for individual projects, ethical definitions had to be formulated, such as the DobeS *Code of Conduct* – on the one hand, for the researchers' field methods and relation to the speakers, and, on the other hand, for the treatment of data when collected, selected, and uploaded to the digital archives. An excerpt of the *Code of Conduct* (Wittenburg, 2005, p. 2, my emphasis) is given here:

- The consultants and communities will be **informed openly** and seriously about the goals of the DOBES program and about the possibilities of misuse.
- In general fieldworkers will document the **agreed mutual understanding** about the nature of the research and the formal consent achieved with the consultants by means of a signed document (...).
- The parties will support efforts for **revitalizing** the languages within the limits of their possibilities.

I personally ran one large documentation project with DobeS on the Baure (Arawakan) language in Bolivian Amazonia (2008–2013)¹² after my individual PhD project with the same language (2003–2007).¹³ Baure is highly endangered with now less than 10, but in 2003 still around 80 speakers. The Baure descendants had specifically requested a linguist who could help them with their language. Their idea was a **revitalization** programme and the development of teaching materials, as I found out on my first field trip. Therefore, even though I was going to write my PhD thesis on the grammar of Baure (with their permission), and I was documenting the language data digitally as annotated videos and audios, I still tried to contribute to the biggest interest of the speakers and produce the pedagogical material on paper and help with the revitalization programme. In our team we developed an array of materials (cf. Table 1), which partly still serve the language teaching in the village today, with the instruction of the local ILC¹⁴.

I felt a large responsibility on my shoulders. I noticed the different access and contact to the global world and academia that I had and the Baure people were so distant to. In those days (2003 and onwards), there was hardly any electricity in the village, let alone telephone or internet connection. Luckily, this has changed completely till the year 2023. One of the typical problems in the **informing** of the speakers we recorded is that they had so little idea of what a digital archive was and who would access the data to what extent. There is the typical ethical paradox that you have to ask all people for permission, while they may never really be aware of the impact their collaboration may have (cf.

¹¹ Institutos de Lengua y Cultura

¹² DobeS, Az. II/83 447 (2008–2011); Az. 85961 (2011–2013)

¹³ This financing came from the Spinoza Prize that Prof. Pieter Muysken, Radboud University Nijmegen, had received for his linguistic work.

¹⁴ Instituto de lengua y cultura.

Dorian 2010: 182). Even though, the recorded speakers left their **mutual agreement** on the audio file or as a separate audio file after the interview, it was from that point on up to the researcher to use common sense and decide which archives were to be excluded from public exposure. It was my first documentation project, I had learnt to speak the language the first years, and I was very ambitious to train the linguistic beginners in the village. Despite of the age of the majority of the Baure speakers, we regularly held meetings, where we discussed the orthography (with mostly illiterate people at that time), where public issues of the language were openly addressed, and books produced in the project were presented. Unfortunately, even though I trained some young students in Baures how to transcribe the language in the ELAN transcription programme, there was not much point, since nobody of the younger generations could speak nor understand this difficult polysynthetic language. I doubt that anybody – apart from Western World linguists – ever accessed the Baure data in the archive.¹⁵

Each situation is different, and each has its own challenges and opportunities. My next documentation project was the PDP – Paunaka Documentation Project, financed as an MDP (*major documentation project*) by ELDP (2011–2013).¹⁶ We applied for the project with the Paunaka speakers and in their favour – the Paunaka language has not yet been included in the list of languages in the Bolivian New Constitution (CPE, 2009), and the project was also designed to create more visibility and leave a proof of the language's existence. Only around 10 speakers could be identified, and only one (very busy and active) person was trained to use the computer and could transcribe the language. In this project, we organized a workshop with all Paunaka descendants and integrated even these non-speakers in the documentation project, e.g. in the decision on the alphabet and with illustrations in the first booklet. Many data were collected, transcribed, translated, linguistically analysed, and articles have been written from many different angles. The linguistic data have been uploaded to the ELAR archive. The archive is sometimes used as a reference for the IPELC, currently applying for the integration of Paunaka in the Constitution.

Looking into the definitions and aims of the ELAR archive itself, we can find the following information on the website:

The Endangered Languages Archive (ELAR) is a digital repository for preserving multimedia collections of endangered languages from all over the world, making them available for future generations.

ELAR's mission is to:

- provide a safe long-term repository for language documentation collections
- train and support depositors in collection creation and preservation
- make collections accessible free of charge to researchers, communities, and the public
- support users in discovering and accessing recordings

In ELAR's collections you can find recordings of every-day conversations, instructions on how to build fish traps or boats, explanations of kinship systems and the use of medicinal plants, and learn about art forms like string figures and sand drawings. ELAR's collections are unique records of local knowledge systems encoded in their languages, described by the holders of the knowledge themselves. (ELAR online, 31/07/2023, my emphasis)

With the Paunaka language, in particular, we have observed that the public archive has helped the language to give a reference to a public and international recognition, which is relevant in the process of the official recognition of Paunaka in the Bolivian Constitution. A number of researchers were grateful to have access to data of yet another Arawakan language for comparative purposes. Only the community itself has little possibility to access the data, and this is due to these reasons:

¹⁵ e.g. this one: "dirty words" in Danielsen et al. 2004 at the <https://archive.mpi.nl/tla>

¹⁶ MDP 0217

- the infrastructure and archive descriptions are only in English;
- no experience with data archives and the architecture of archives;
- no knowledge of the data file format and the idea of a “session” to which more than one file belongs (complexity).

Finally, I had another large documentation project with a Bolivian language, which allowed somewhat more inclusion of the indigenous community members, the GIZAC project with the two Tupi-Guarani languages Guarayu and Guarasu Ñe’e, also ELDP (2014-2017).¹⁷ This project serves as a special case study in the next section, and here, I only want to summarize the achievements of this and the other projects in Table 1, which would not have been possible without my extended teams consisting of German and Bolivian student assistants, interns, and the main team members, PhD, MA, and BA students.¹⁸

	Baure	Paunaka	Guarayu
digital archive	+	+	+
books & booklets	4	1	1
posters	3	1	1
active participation of speakers	(+)	(+)	+
PhDs	3+	1	
MAAs & BAs	5	1	2
scientific articles	>50	>10	ca. 10
my articles	20	4	3
in Spanish	4	1	1

Table 1: Rough output from my documentation projects

The outcomes from my projects were guided by statements like the following:

We cannot maintain the divisions between ‘us’ as the researcher and ‘them’ as the subjects of research. Fieldwork and language documentation is the ultimate social act in a system of exchange. So, we have to make **reciprocity** central and not peripheral to what we do, negotiating the conduct of our projects, and outcomes, **making the documentation usable and valuable**, and **giving back in ways that are meaningful and valuable to the communities**. Ethical behaviour or even advocacy (supporting communities, writing letters, and advocating for them) is not enough. Ideally, researchers should share their knowledge and be prepared to help communities to support their languages if they wish to do so. (Austin 2010: 49-50, my emphasis)

It is important to have the speaker in mind with all the outcomes of our research:

The Beneficence Principle rests on the obligation of researchers to take due diligence to protect human subjects from harm and to maximize the possible benefit of the research to the human subject and the larger society (Protection of Human Subjects, 2009). (Agunloye 2019: 171)

Certainly, we can declare aims and have ethical demands on us as researchers, but we also have to be realistic and live with a number of obstacles. And, as others have already stated, the digital archives as such are not really that accessible for the speech communities. Valdovinos (2017) argues that

“la manera en la que se presentan los archivos ante el público deja más bien la impresión de que el único fin realmente atendido corresponde al de la investigación. Este giro puede

¹⁷ MDP 0299

¹⁸ The list would probably be lacking someone, so it is not explicit here, but please refer to the individual projects to find the individual contributors.

observarse en las políticas de almacenamiento y de acceso de las colecciones.” (Valdovinos, 2017: p. 226)¹⁹

This is crucial: the access to the data via a complicated process of registration and login until finding the data, even though this is certainly done for the safety of the data. For the speakers I have worked with, the participation in this long process is unthinkable, no matter how much I would assist them or show them the steps.

In order to access the data in the mentioned archives, in order to first of all find the data or be aware of them, various steps have to be taken, and these seem to contain a number of obstacles for the local Bolivian communities:

- find the page: in Spanish Google on a smartphone, you might not find the archive pages under the top entries;
- view the infrastructure: the archive pages may not present a good overview on the smartphone and it may not be clear how to access data and what there is to access; problem with the metalanguage English;
- register as a user: metalanguage English; need of an e-mail account (while today, everyone uses messengers); roles you might not be able to fill in (academic, teacher, etc.)
- approval: if you receive an e-mail, you can enter the archive, but the mail may arrive in the junk folder; the mailing language is English;²⁰
- data formats: the different programmes used by the linguists are not all useful for non-experts (such as heavy video and audio formats; eaf (ELAN), or trs (Transcriber), or other extensions); the linguistic analysis is very specialized and needs again extra keys to decipher.

The question is how many non-linguists or non-experts have the patience to follow all these steps, only for taking a look at some (for them) boring elicitations on verbal forms or the like? Just like Valdovinos (2017, p. 228) resumes, this is not very encouraging for the speakers of the communities we have worked with:

Finalmente, la exigencia del proceso de registro no parece ser muy alentadora para aquellos individuos provenientes de las comunidades rurales en donde se hablan las lenguas cuya documentación está archivada. Esto se debe principalmente a su falta de experiencia de gestión, es decir, la falta de conocimientos que les permitan entender el funcionamiento y la razón de llenar un cuestionario con datos personales. En todos los casos parece curioso también el hecho de que, a pesar de que se predica la promoción y el uso de las lenguas nativas, en ninguno de estos archivos aparezca un esfuerzo por presentar los materiales o las instrucciones para acceder a dichos materiales en tales lenguas. (Valdovinos, 2017, p. 228)²¹

Thus, we have to find alternative and more participatory ways in order to keep what we promise when trying ethical language investigation and documentation in the times of decolonization.

¹⁹ English translation: the way in which the archives are presented to the public rather leaves the impression that the only purpose they really served is that of research. This orientation can be seen in the storage and access policies of the collections.

²⁰ In addition, people in Bolivia should actually refrain from downloading anything because of the wide-spread virus problem and all devices are in constant danger of getting infected.

²¹ English translation: Finally, the requirement of the registration process does not seem to be very encouraging for those individuals coming from the rural communities where the languages whose documentation is on file are spoken. This is mainly due to their lack of management experience, that is, the lack of knowledge that allows them to understand how it works and the reason for filling out a questionnaire with personal data. In all cases, it also seems curious that, despite the fact that the promotion and use of native languages is preached, in none of these archives does an effort appear to present the materials or the instructions to access said materials in those languages.

Age and gender

Men 46.50%
Women 53.50%

Location

Towns/cities

Countries

Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia	1,010
Ascensión, Bolivia	127
Buenos Aires, Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires, Argentina	23
Cochabamba, Bolivia	17
São Paulo, SP, Brazil	12

Figure 1: The community of followers in Facebook of the page *Gwarayu Ñe'ësa* (10/08/2023)

On this FB page, I share all updates concerning the Guaranay language, such as publications, public presentations (sometimes with streaming), other related projects, and I ask the community to evaluate products and publications. Through this page, I share documents and links, and it has become very useful as a platform of interaction. In 2020, when Covid-19 arrived in Bolivia, the FB page was an important instrument for information on local sanitary practices, e.g., by providing texts in Guaranay²⁴ explaining the pandemic and proposed measures, offering mask sewing workshops in my house (people saw it and came to my house, and we sew masks together), spreading masks and food donations, raising more donations, etc. In the solitude of Covid in Bolivia, *Gwarayu Ñe'ësa* became a platform of exchange and remains till today.

6.3 Republication on a local basis

As argued above (§5), academic publications on indigenous languages are most often in the English language. Even though some Bolivians may read these texts – and lately, they can make use of the AI translation software – Latin Americans need publications in Spanish or Portuguese. In addition, the publications have to be accessible, i.e. people have to be aware of them and find them on a local basis. I have been publishing on Bolivian indigenous languages in English and Spanish since 2006. Only very

²⁴ Thanks to the Guaranay speaker from Urubichá Pedro Yaquirena, living in Spain in 2020, who wrote a page of instructions in Guaranay.

few articles could be presented in a Bolivian linguistic journal in Spanish (*Revista páginas & signos*, Universidad Mayor de San Simón, Cochabamba).²⁵ However, such special magazines are not the reading matter of people in Bolivian villages. Since 2020, I have therefore been publishing the journal *Gwarayu Ñe'ësa* – same name as the FB page in §6.2 –, which provides paper and digital issues on all my publications of the Guarayu language.²⁶ The paper issues are given to all the basic institutions and sold for little money to interested people. The digital issues are uploaded for free access as online publications on the Zenodo platform, where they have been downloaded by between 108 and 444 readers. I am also aiming at republishing other articles, if they are on and about the Guarayu language or people, in the journal, and other articles, I upload them and share the link on the Facebook page. This strategy has proven to be very successful on a local basis, and I get very positive feedback.

Figure 2: The Facebook page and the five issues of the locally published journal

7. Final remarks

After all, what we haven't managed yet in Bolivia is the creation of a national archive for the storing of all linguistic data collected by so many foreign experts. In other countries, this is starting, like in Argentina or Mexico, but in Bolivia, the people are still working quite separately from each other. One project that is currently bringing together Bolivian researchers, language experts, and foreign investigators in linguistics, is the Linguistics Summer School of Bolivia (LSSB)²⁷. The discipline of linguistics is growing in Bolivia, especially at the PROEIB Andes institute, based at the University of Cochabamba, where students can write their MA and PhD in sociolinguistics and intercultural education, and at the two large universities in La Paz and El Alto, where mainly Aymara and Quechua are being studied. After having obtained a certificate from these places, students often go abroad and

²⁵ <https://umss.academia.edu/RevistaPáginaySignos>

²⁶ I have also been inspired by my colleague Franziska Riedel, who publishes a collaborative journal with local people in Baures: *To Washor – Revista Cultural de Concepción de Baures*. The anthropologist and her co-editors publish texts by the people and their own essays that they elaborate only for this journal. Thus, the objective is somewhat different.

²⁷ <https://www.schoolandcollegelists.com/BO/Cochabamba/525783554241586/Linguistics-Summer-School-Bolivia> (11/08/2023)

continue their linguistic career; at the same time they keep in touch with the Bolivian society and language communities, so that there is the hope that there will be many more linguistic publications produced by Bolivians, including native speakers of indigenous languages, in the future. There is still a long way to proper participation and active research and documentation by the speakers of indigenous languages themselves, in Bolivia or Latin America. The digitization is yet incomplete or distributed unevenly and teachers should play a role in preparing the communities for future digital activities. Last but not least, “[t]o navigate the transition to a digital world of work and thrive in it, individuals need not only digital skills but also a broad mix of skills, including cognitive and socio-emotional skills” (OECD 2020: 159).

The ethical aims have been declared, but it is not always easy to fulfil them. There are some contradictions to our good intentions:

- When data are collected and stored, it is impossible to anticipate all future uses of the data;
- Future use may become harmful to the human subjects due to errors in the re-use and the inferences made. (Agunloye 2019: 173)

What Agunloye argues, is true for all our information we throw into the online world. To improve this, the whole digital behaviour in society must be adapted and changed eventually.

I am grateful to all I have learnt through the collaboration with the speakers of such diverse languages. It never felt right to just go out into the field and study something that I would find interesting without open ears and eyes for the interest and needs of the same people I was interviewing. I am glad that the possibilities to participate have improved through the participation in a digital world. However, I am also aware of the difficulties people growing up in more isolated environments are facing when trying to connect to a(n online) world we are acting in day by day.

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